

Intriguing Meaning of the Demographic Studies: An Empirical Study

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Abstract:

Demography studies the trends and processes associated with the population. The importance of demography lies in its contribution in helping government and society as a means of analyzing and predicting social, cultural and economic trends related to population. In policy making, understanding the demographic profile and population helps in framing the right policies which would be in favour of the masses. In this backdrop, the present study focused on demographic profile two states viz. Gujarat and Goa.

Keywords: Demography, Analysis, Masses, Trends, Processes

Introduction

Demographic features influence the insight of respondents. So it is important to discuss the profile of the community as it provides the study with a proper perspective and brought out its various features. Thus, in this project an attempt has been made to highlight the demographic characteristics from state Gujarat and Goa. Socio-economic features of the community have vital implications as they provide the knowledge of general behaviour and attitude of people and throw light on problems and prospects. Moreover, these socio-economic features offer important clues and insights for devising suitable policy for

future to advance and increase facilities of the society. The results of any study depend upon the individual, family, career and organizational profile of the respondents. The empirical study consists of 60 respondents'- 30 each from state Gujarat and Goa State.

Research Methodology

Research methodology is the procedure to systematically solve the research issue. It is a way, structure, method for examination conceived so as to get replies to the research inquiries. This study had an explanatory research design and its purpose was to explore the various socio-economic aspects associated with changing status of population that remained unexplored. The objective of the present study has been accomplished with the help of primary sources of data. The primary source has been collected through questionnaire included responses from the different categories of masses. The data has been collected from 60 respondents in the study area.

Descriptive statistics was employed to analyse and present the socio-economic characteristics. It involved frequency, per centage distribution. Apart from this, One sample t-test has been used to compare means of different socio-economic variables between two States (Gujarat & Goa) of study area in order to draw the precise inferences.

Results and Discussion

In any research, the discussion of the profile of the community to be studied is an essential work because it provided the study with a proper perspective and brought out its various features. Therefore, in the present article, an attempt was made to present a socio-economic profile of the masses from these two states. Individual profile covered in the study area is age, marital status, educational qualification, monthly income, type of family, nature of family, nature of service etc. It gives a clear picture of career profile.

Age of Respondents

Age is one of the essential variables; it defines normal behaviour and professional commitment of people. Age plays an important role in the social position. The younger population performed different sets of social and familiar functions as compared to older population.

Table No. - Age of Respondents

S.No	Age	Gujarat		Goa	
		No. of Respondents	%age	No. of Respondents	%age
01.	Under 15 Yrs	01	3.3	02	6.7
02.	15 To 20 Yrs	06	20.0	11	36.7
03.	21 To 26 Yrs	08	26.7	11	36.7
04.	Above 26 Yrs	15	50.0	06	20.0
Total		30	100	30	100

Source: Compiled by Authors from Primary Survey

It was important to know about the age of population. The above table presents the age composition of the sample under study. It is found that in case of State Gujarat majority of the people i.e. 50.0 per cent (n=15) belonged to age group 26 years and above, 26.7 per cent (n=08) belonged to age group of 21-26 years, only 20 per cent (n=06) belonged to age group 15-20 Years. Similarly, from State Goa it is found that almost 37 per cent (n=11) each belonged to age group 15-20 years and 21-26 Years, 20.0 per cent (n=66) belonged to age group 26 years and above, 6.7 per cent (n=02) belonged to age group of under 15 years. The people of age group 26 and above years displayed strong

physical endurance, more confidence level and provided more time and energy, in order to become good educators like teachers, doctors, scientists’ engineers, etc. social servants with latest trends and techniques. The people with younger age group said that the energetic and active mind helped them to perform duties energetically.

Gender of Respondents

S.No	Gender	Gujarat		Goa	
		No. of Respondents	%age	No. of Respondents	%age
01.	Male	23	76.7	14	46.7
02.	Female	07	23.3	16	53.3
Total		30	100	30	100

Source: Compiled by Authors from Primary Survey

Educational status is an important factor in the life. Education was related to people’s aspirations, feeling of obligation to society, upward social mobility and a desire for a sense of competence and fulfilment. The basic and formal education was always considered as an important route for a successful career. It was seen that as education, profession and economy were closely

related with each other so were professional education, modernization and technology. The educational background of people gave an insight into the cultural level of family and their preparedness to perform the various activities related to any professional role. The professional education was the best source of people for acquiring more modernized skill and knowledge necessary for the upliftment of young generation.

Table No. – Educational qualification of Respondents

S.No	Educational Qualification	Gujarat		Goa	
		No. of Respondents	%age	No. of Respondents	%age
01.	High school	12	40.0	10	33.3
02.	Bachelor's Degree	08	26.7	12	40.0
03.	Master's Degree	05	16.7	03	10.0
04.	Ph.D. or Higher	01	3.3	02	6.7
05.	Any Other	04	13.3	03	10.0
Total		30	100	30	100

Source: Compiled by Authors from Primary Survey

It is depicted from the above result table that in Gujarat maximum number of people i.e. almost 40 per cent (n=12) was having High school qualification while as 26.7 per cent (n=08) were having Bachelor's degree, 16.7 per cent (n=05) have completed master's degree. Similarly, in case of Goa state almost 40 per cent (n=12) of population is having Bachelor's degree and 33.3 per cent (n=10) were have completed High school.

Marital Status of Respondents

S.No	Marital Status	Gujarat		Goa	
		No. of Respondents	%age	No. of Respondents	%age
01.	Married	24	80.00	16	53.3
02.	Unmarried	06	20.0	14	46.7
03.	Divorced	00	0.00	00	0.00
04.	Widowed	00	0.00	00	0.00
Total		30	100	30	100

Source: Compiled by Authors from Primary Survey

While distributing on the basis of marital status of people, it is found that in Gujarat almost 80 per cent (n=24) of surveyed people were married. 20 per cent (n=06) of the people were unmarried, no per centage of surveyed people were neither divorced nor separated. While in case of Goa, it is found that almost 53.3 per cent (n=16) of survey people were married, 46.7 per cent (n=14) were unmarried, and no per centage of surveyed people were neither divorced nor separated. The surveyed people who were married lived with their husbands and children. Some of the surveyed people lived in joint families and thus resided with in-laws and other family members.

During research investigation, it is found that surveyed people are engaged in different types of services. Thus here we tried to highlight the nature of services they have, which is presented in table below.

Employment Status of Respondents

S.No	Employment Status	Gujarat		Goa	
		No. of Respondents	%age	No. of Respondents	%age
01.	Student	03	10.0	12	40.0
02.	Part-Time Employed	03	10.0	02	6.7
03.	Full-Time Employed	04	13.3	03	10.0
04.	Unemployed	02	6.7	02	6.7
05.	Retired	00	0.00	01	3.3
06.	Self-Employed	18	60.0	10	33.3
	Total	30	100	30	100

Source: Compiled by Authors from Primary Survey

The above table depicts the classification of respondents on the basis of nature of service. In Gujarat, it is found that majority of surveyed people 60 per cent (n=18) were Self-Employed, 13.3 per cent (n=04) were Full-time employed and 10 per cent each (n=03) of were working on Part-Time Employment and student. However, it is revealed from the results that in Goa around 40 per cent (n=12) of surveyed people were enjoying student life, nearly 33.3 per cent (n=10) were self-employed and 10 per cent (n=03) of surveyed population were working on full-time employment basis.

Economic Status of Respondents

Economic status of people play crucial role to understand the relevance of income to various activities. The people during their studies were financed by their parents for acquiring professional skills of higher order. It was due to sound economic status of family, the young and talented youth developed a

sense of an innovative ability. This innovative ability helped them in the expression of their identity.

S.No	Annual Income	Gujarat		Goa	
		No. of Respondents	%age	No. of Respondents	%age
01.	Less Than 20,000	14	46.7	12	40.0
02.	21,000- 30,000	08	26.7	09	30.0
03.	31,000-40,000	01	3.3	03	10.0
04.	41,000-50,000	02	6.7	03	10.0
05.	Above 50,000	05	16.7	03	10.0
Total		30	100	30	100

Source: Compiled by Authors from Primary Survey

While distributing on the basis of annual income of respondents, it is found from the results that in Gujarat majority of respondents' i.e. 46.7 per cent (n=14) earning income less than Rs 20,000 per year. There were 26.7 per cent (n=08) of respondents whose annual income was between Rs 21,000 and Rs 30,000 per year, 16.7 per cent (n=05) of respondents earning income above 50,000 per year and only 6.7 per cent (n=02) of respondents earning income between 41,000 to 50,000 per year. However, in case of Goa, it is found that majority of surveyed people i.e. 40 per cent (n=12) earning income less than Rs 20,000 per year and there were almost 30 per cent (n=09) of respondents earning an income between Rs 21,000 and Rs 30,000 per year. 10 per cent (n=03) of surveyed people earning income between Rs 31,000 and above per year. The sound and higher income provided people an independence and authority for utilization of own earnings in a proper way. Most of the surveyed people spent income for the purpose of giving basic, professional education to their children, other family activities etc.

Household Size of Respondents

Family plays an important role in everyone's existence. Family influences the life style of their children. It provides the environment which motivates and shapes their desires and aims. The family provides care, supervision and education. The nature and status of people is very much dependent upon the type of family they belongs to. They enjoy family life and spent time with their family members. Women teachers were contented, peaceful and lived happy home life. The women sense of identity came from their professional role. They devote time to family duties and responsibilities, but at the same time it is true that their style of living is work oriented. Thus, family plays vital role in creating women leaders.

S.No	Household Size	Gujarat		Goa	
		No. of Respondents	%age	No. of Respondents	%age
01.	2 People	00	0.00	04	13.3
02.	3-4 People	16	53.3	09	30.0
03.	5-7 People	10	33.3	14	46.7
04.	7 & More People	04	13.3	03	10.0
	Total	30	100	30	100

Source: Compiled by Authors from Primary Survey

The above table presents the classification of the respondents on the basis of type of families they belong to. It is found that in Gujarat almost 53.3 per cent (n=16) of respondents resided in nuclear families having 3-4 people where as 33.3 per cent (n=10) of respondents resided in families having 5-7 people. However in Goa around 46.7 per cent (n=14) of respondents resided in families having 5-7 people and nearly 30 per cent (n=09) of respondents resided in families having 3-4 people. This means that a lower per centage live in joint families and majority lives in nuclear families.

Parental Status of Respondents

S.No	Parental Status	Gujarat		Goa	
		No. of Respondents	%age	No. of Respondents	%age
01.	Parent	18	60.0	14	46.7
02.	Not a Parent	08	26.7	16	53.3
03.	Any Other	04	13.3	00	0.00
Total		30	100	30	100

Source: Compiled by Authors from Primary Survey

While distributing on the basis of parental status of people, it is found that in Gujarat almost 60 per cent (n=18) of surveyed people were parents. 26.7 per cent (n=08) of the people were not a parent, 13.3 per cent of surveyed people were either single mother or father only. While in case of Goa, it is found that almost 53.3 per cent (n=16) of survey people were not a parent, 46.7 per cent (n=14) were parents and no per centage of surveyed people were either found single father or mother. The surveyed people who were married lived with their husbands and children. Some of the surveyed people lived with parents and thus resided with in-laws and other family members.

Religious Affiliation of Respondents

S.No	Religious Affiliation	Gujarat		Goa	
		No. of Respondents	%age	No. of Respondents	%age
01.	Christianity	01	3.3	10	33.3
02.	Hinduism	25	83.3	15	50.0
03.	Islam	02	6.7	05	16.7
04.	Sikhism	01	3.3	00	0.00
05.	Buddhism	01	3.3	00	0.00
06.	Any Other	00	0.00	00	0.00
Total		30	100	30	100

Source: Compiled by Authors from Primary Survey

While distributing on the basis of religion status of people, it is found that in Gujarat almost 83.3 per cent (n=25) of surveyed people were following Hinduism, 6.7 per cent (n=02) of the people were following Islam, 3.3 per cent of surveyed people were following Christianity, Sikhism and Buddhism. While in case of Goa, it is found that almost 50.0 per cent (n=15) of survey people were obeying Hinduism, 33.3 per cent (n=10) were following Christianity, and 16.7 per cent of surveyed people were following Islam. From the results it is found that among surveyed people no one is found from the Sikhism and Buddhism.

Living status of Respondents

S.No	Living Status	Gujarat		Goa	
		No. of Respondents	%age	No. of Respondents	%age
01.	HomeOwner	25	83.3	17	56.7
02.	Renter	05	16.7	12	40.0
03.	Lessee	00	0.00	00	0.00
04.	AnyOther	00	0.00	01	3.3
Total		30	100	30	100

Source: Compiled by Authors from Primary Survey

While distributing on the basis of living Status of respondents, it is found from the results that in Gujarat majority of respondents' i.e. 83.3 per cent (n=25) were homeowners. There were 16.7 per cent (n=05) of respondents who were renters, no one from Gujarat were lessee. However, in case of Goa, it is found that majority of surveyed people i.e. 56.7 per cent (n=17) were homeowners and there were almost 40 per cent (n=12) of respondents were renters. 3.3 per cent (n=01) of surveyed people were having other living status.

Vote Registration of Respondents

S.No	Registered To Vote	Gujarat		Goa	
		No. of Respondents	%age	No. of Respondents	%age
01.	Yes	28	93.3	22	73.3
02.	No	02	6.7	08	26.7
Total		30	100	30	100

Source: Compiled by Authors from Primary Survey

While distributing on the basis of Registration to vote of people, it is found that in Gujarat almost 93.3 per cent (n=28) of surveyed people were registered to vote while as only 6.7 per cent (n=02) of the people were not registered to vote. While in case of Goa, it is found that almost 73.3 per cent (n=22) of survey people were registered to vote while as 26.7 per cent of surveyed people were not registered to vote.

Disability Status of Respondents

S.No	Disability	Gujarat		Goa	
		No. of Respondents	%age	No. of Respondents	%age
01.	Yes	05	16.7	04	13.3
02.	No	25	83.3	26	86.7
Total		30	100	30	100

Source: Compiled by Authors from Primary Survey

While distributing on the basis of disability of people, it is found that in Gujarat almost 83.3 per cent (n=25) of surveyed people are not having any disability while as only 16.7 per cent (n=05) of the people were having disability. While in case of Goa, it is found that almost 86.7 per cent (n=26) of survey people were not having any disability while as 13.3 per cent of surveyed people were having any sort of disability like anxiety, blood pressure etc.

T-Test Results

Difference in Socio-Economic Variables in two groups/ states (Gujarat & Goa)

The socio-cultural beliefs and infrastructural development have resulted into unequal and irrational distribution of infrastructure in the region leading to the emergence of regional disparities in economic, social and cultural mosaic (Hungaragi, 2008)

This study employed t-test to analyse the mean difference in different socio-economic variables of respondents. The problem of regional disparity in socio-economic infrastructure is a universal phenomenon. Thus, an attempt has been made to highlight the disparity in socio-economic status of individuals which are influencing the attitude of people in different states.

1.- Difference in Average Monthly Income between two states (Gujarat and Goa)

H_0 - There is no significant difference in average monthly income between two states (Gujarat & Goa).

H_1 – There is significant difference in average monthly income between two states (Gujarat & Goa).

Infrastructure development leads to reduction in inequities of income. Income disparity directly impacts the socio-economic status of individuals and their spouses. Various previous studies have found that augmentation in

infrastructure services has reduced the inequities in income and poverty. **Banerjee and Somanathan (2007)** analysed the impact of accessibility to infrastructure services on the distribution of income and showed that these two are positively related that is the benefits of infrastructure services were mostly accrued in higher income groups as opposed to benefitting the poor. The difference in average monthly income between two states (Gujarat & Goa) is presented in table below.

Table No.- Difference in average monthly income between two states (Gujarat & Goa)

Region	N	Mean	S.D	d. f	t-value	Sig.
Gujarat	30	55,830.33	3470.2	29	8.229	0.00
Goa	30	59,350.88	3723.7	29	7.870	0.00

From the results, it is found that t-value for monthly income is 8.229 and 7.870 in states Gujarat and Goa respectively, whose significant value is 0.000 (i.e. $p=0.000$) which is less than 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is statistically significant difference in the mean monthly income of respondents in two states. Therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the mean monthly income of respondents is rejected and the alternate hypothesis is accepted. Moreover, the mean value of income in Gujarat is 55,830 rupees monthly and the mean value of income in Goa is 59,350 rupees monthly with standard deviation 3470.2 and 3723.7 respectively. Thus, from the mean value it is evident that Goa has better economic status than Gujarat. Thus, it can be concluded that monthly income of different respondents belonging to these two states is significantly different.

Difference in Average Educational Qualification between two states (Gujarat and Goa)

Educational status is an influential instrument in a society for overcoming inequalities, promoting human development, accelerating social transformation and achieving economic progress (**Kumar, 2009**). Educational infrastructure leads to better achievement of social status, economic growth, modernization in society, empowerment of weaker sections and community as a whole. It improves the development indicators consistently, as it is one of the most important social characteristics (**Bhola, 1987**).

H₀ - There is no significant difference in average educational qualification between two States (Gujarat & Goa).

H₁ - There is significant difference in average educational qualification between two States (Gujarat & Goa).

Table No. 4.11- Difference in average educational qualification between two States (Gujarat & Goa).

Region	N	Mean	S.D	df	t-value	Sig.
Gujarat	30	1.500	.5145	29	12.369	0.00
Goa	30	1.555	.5113	29	12.907	0.00

From the results, it is found that t-value for educational qualification is 12.369 and 12.907 in States Gujarat & Goa respectively, whose significant value is 0.000 (i.e. $p=.000$) which is less than 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is statistically significant difference in the mean educational qualification of respondents in two states. Therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the mean educational qualification of respondents is

rejected and the alternate hypothesis is accepted. Moreover, the mean value of educational qualification in Gujarat is 1.500 and the mean value of educational qualification in Goa is 1.555 with standard deviation .5145 and .5113 respectively. Thus, from the mean value it is evident that Goa has better educational status than Gujarat. Thus, it can be concluded that educational qualification of different respondents belonging to these two states is significantly different.

The problem of disparity in the levels of demographic background is a common phenomenon. The rural-urban upbringing was a significant component in the life of people. Results indicated that most respondents were from urban areas. They had spent life's most time in the city atmosphere thus become cultured and civilised citizens with active and innovative thinking. The people residing in urban areas were comparatively broadminded and liberal in view. Such atmosphere helped them in understanding the economic, social, cultural and political rights to save themselves from humiliation and exploitation.

Thus, the socio-economic features reflected overall insight into personality, attitude of respondents and identified the potential of population for development. Both married and unmarried categories were found and also from different communities like Muslims, Sikh and Hindu etc. Most of them had completed post-graduation degrees, qualified National Eligibility Test (NET), Junior Research Fellowship (JRF). The M.Phil and Ph.D. degree holders were also found and they all were experienced in their concerned subjects. The socio-cultural profile of the people suggested that they were homogeneous group of individuals with similar educational background. What emerged as a significant factor was the strong desire with an urge to give exposure to talents and skills and to achieve something unique. The sound economic, educational

and occupational background of parents encouraged them to accept the challenging professions like teaching, medical etc.

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